

The Random Ray Method for Problems with Strong Transport Effect

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ABSTRACT

The transport effect, characterized by strong anisotropy in the neutron angular flux, is a fundamental challenge in reactor physics calculations. Deterministic methods, such as the Discrete Ordinates (S_N) and Method of Characteristics (MOC), struggle with these problems, often suffering from unphysical ray effects due to fixed angular discretization. The Random Ray Method (TRRM), a variant of MOC, replaces the deterministic angular quadrature with a stochastic sampling of characteristic rays. This approach effectively smooths the angular phase space, inherently eliminating the ray effects that plague traditional methods. In this study, we investigate the capability of TRRM to resolve strong transport effect by applying it to a challenging lattice benchmark problem using our self-developed code, THETA. The problem geometry features a checkerboard pattern of strong absorbers, specifically designed to create narrow streaming channels and severe flux anisotropy. Numerical results demonstrate that while conventional MOC calculations exhibit significant ray effects in this problem, TRRM successfully captures the complex, anisotropic flux distribution without such artifacts. We confirm that the accuracy of TRRM is governed by statistical uncertainty, not by angular discretization error, and this uncertainty can be systematically reduced by increasing the total tracking length. Furthermore, we identify an improved computational strategy: for a fixed total tracking length, employing a larger number of rays per batch with a shorter individual tracking length minimizes batch-to-batch statistical fluctuations and reduces the final uncertainty. This work validates TRRM as a robust and high-fidelity method for strongly anisotropic transport problems.

Keywords: Transport effect, anisotropy, the random ray method

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate reactor physics calculation is fundamental to nuclear reactor design, safety analysis, and core operations. In many practical applications, particularly in regions with high material heterogeneity or strong absorbers, the neutron angular flux exhibits significant variation with direction. This phenomenon, which is called transport effect, invalidates the widely used diffusion approximation and necessitates a high-fidelity solution to the transport equation. Such scenarios are common in modern reactor designs, including fuel-moderator interfaces, control rod assemblies, and burnable poison pins within a fuel lattice.

The key characteristic of transport effect is the strong anisotropy in the neutron angular flux. Capturing this directional dependency accurately and efficiently is a significant challenge for different transport methods. The Spherical Harmonics (P_N) method [1], which expands the angular flux in a series of spherical harmonics, struggles with highly forward-peaked or rapidly varying angular distributions unless an impractically high expansion order is employed. The Discrete Ordinates (S_N) method [2] and the Method of Characteristics (MOC) [3] are more robust for such problems as they discretize the angular domain directly. However, both S_N and MOC are susceptible to ray effect [4]. These unphysical oscillations in the angular flux are caused by the use of a finite, discrete set of directions, and they become particularly severe in problems where transport effects are pronounced. The Monte Carlo

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method can accurately handle problems with strong transport effects. However, for radiation shielding problems where such effects are ubiquitous due to the presence of strong absorbers and low-density media, Monte Carlo method suffers from the issue of excessively high variance in deep-penetration regions.

To overcome the limitations of deterministic angular discretization, the Random Ray Method (TRRM) [5], a variant of MOC, has emerged as a promising alternative. The fundamental advantage of the TRRM lies in its unique treatment of the angular variable. Instead of relying on a fixed angular quadrature, the TRRM employs a stochastic sampling of characteristic rays. This random sampling effectively smooths the angular phase space, thereby inherently eliminating the ray effects that plague S_N and MOC methods. This approach allows for a high-fidelity representation of complex and highly anisotropic angular fluxes without the unphysical artifacts of discrete angle sets or the high-order requirements of P_N expansions. Previous studies on TRRM [6][7] in shielding-like scenarios have preliminarily demonstrated its accuracy for such problems, yet these investigations have not placed significant focus on the detailed treatment of the angular phase space.

Therefore, in this study, we provide a more refined investigation into the capability of TRRM to resolve strong transport effects by specifically analyzing how stochastic angular sampling parameters influence the solution of a challenging benchmark. We apply the method to a challenging lattice problem characterized by strong absorption [8]. By analyzing the performance of the TRRM on this problem, we aim to demonstrate its effectiveness and robustness in accurately capturing the strong flux anisotropy. The TRRM calculations are performed using our self-developed code, THETA (Tracking-based Hybrid monte carlo-moc Efficient Tracking Application).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 gives the description of MOC and TRRM about its angular treatment. Section 3 presents the numerical results of TRRM. Section 4 gives the summary of this study.

2. METHODOLOGY

The theoretical foundation of the Random Ray Method (TRRM) is the Method of Characteristics (MOC), which solves the Boltzmann transport equation along many characteristic rays in different directions. Based on the well-known multi-group approximation and Flat-Source Region (FSR) approximation, the steady-state Boltzmann equation along a single characteristic ray of given direction can be simplified to an ordinary equation. This equation can be solved analytically for a segment formed by the intersection of the ray with an FSR:

$$\psi_{g,i,l,k}(s) = \psi_{g,i,l,k}(0) \exp^{-\Sigma_{t,g,i}s} + \frac{Q_{g,i}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}} (1 - \exp^{-\Sigma_{t,g,i}s}) \quad (1)$$

where g is the index of energy group, i is the index of FSR, l is the index of this characteristic ray, k is the index of segment that l -th ray intersects with i -th FSR. s is the location variable. $\psi_{g,i,l,k}(0)$ is the incoming angular flux of this segment. $\Sigma_{t,g,i}$ and $Q_{g,i}$ are the group-wised total cross-section and source strength in the i -th FSR, respectively.

The averaged angular flux in this segment is calculated by:

$$\bar{\psi}_{g,i,l,k} = \frac{Q_{g,i}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}} + \frac{(1 - \exp^{-\Sigma_{t,g,i}s_{l,k}})}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}s_{l,k}} \left[\psi_{g,i,l,k}(0) - \frac{Q_{g,i}}{\Sigma_{t,g,i}} \right] \quad (2)$$

where $s_{l,k}$ is the length of this segment.

The fundamental task of any transport method is to compute the region-averaged scalar flux. For a given FSR i , the scalar flux is the integral of the angular flux over the full 4π solid angle:

$$\phi_{g,i} = \int_{4\pi} \psi_{g,i}(\Omega) d\Omega \quad (3)$$

In the problems with strong transport effect, $\psi_{g,i}(\Omega)$ is far from isotropic, and MOC approximate this anisotropy using a fixed, deterministic angular quadrature set:

$$\phi_{g,i} \approx \sum_{m=1}^M w_m \bar{\psi}_{g,i}(\Omega_m) \quad (4)$$

where M is the number of directions in the quadrature set, Ω_m and w_m is a direction and its corresponding weight in the quadrature set. $\bar{\psi}_{g,i}(\Omega_m)$ is the averaged flux of Ω_m for i -th FSR, which is the sum of Equation (2) for all rays with direction Ω_m .

The MOC typically employs a product quadrature set, which separates the integral over the solid angle into integrals over the polar angle and azimuthal angle. The determination of the azimuthal quadrature set is straightforward, where the azimuthal angles are uniformly distributed in the xy -plane. The determination of polar angle quadrature is more sophisticated. Currently, the commonly used polar angle quadrature set is the Tabuchi-Yamamoto (TY)[9] quadrature sets. After determining the angle quadrature set, numerous equally-spaced parallel characteristic rays are generated and tracked.

While inheriting the fundamental theory of MOC, TRRM completely abandons the deterministic angle quadrature of traditional MOC. In TRRM, characteristic rays are generated by sampling their starting positions and directions independently and uniformly within the phase space. This process is analogous to Monte Carlo integration, and Equation (3) in TRRM is re-written as:

$$\phi_{g,i} \approx \frac{4\pi}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N \sum_{k \in l} \bar{\psi}_{g,i,l,k} \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of rays used for TRRM calculation.

This stochastic approach provides two features:

- **Elimination of Ray Effects:** By continuously re-sampling the angular domain, TRRM does not rely on a fixed set of directions. Over a sufficient number of samples, the probability of "missing" an angular peak approaches zero.
- **Statistical Convergence:** The accuracy of the solution is no longer limited by the angular discretization error of a fixed quadrature set. Instead, it is governed by statistical uncertainty, which can be reduced by increasing the number of random rays or the distance that a ray travelled.

Consequently, the TRRM is expected to have a considerable advantage in addressing problems dominated by strong transport effects. This will be demonstrated in the following section using a highly challenging problem. A self-developed code THETA is utilized for numerical investigation. THETA is a three-dimensional particle transport code based on TRRM, whose objective is to investigate and explore the potential of TRRM for addressing challenges in reactor core physics calculations and radiation shielding calculations. THETA implements an efficient 3D ray tracing on structured Cartesian grid and is designed with a domain decomposition parallelization strategy to leverage modern high-performance computing (HPC) architectures.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Problem Description

The problem selected in this study is a lattice geometry problem [8], which is specifically designed to induce severe angular anisotropy through the arrangement of purely absorbing materials. The geometry, illustrated in Figure 1, consists of a 7 cm × 7 cm square domain. At the center of this domain is a 1 cm × 1 cm region (designated "Red") that functions as the neutron source. This source is surrounded by a checkerboard pattern of 1 cm × 1 cm strong absorber regions (designated "Black"). The remainder of the domain is filled with a purely scattering medium (designated "Blue"). The cross-sections (XSs) for different regions are tabulated in Table I. Furthermore, vacuum boundary conditions are applied to all external boundaries of the square domain.

The arrangement of strong absorbers creates narrow channels through the scattering medium. Neutrons that originate from the central source are highly restricted and can only escape the inner lattice by streaming through these gaps. This physical behavior results in highly anisotropic neutron angular flux. This high degree of angular anisotropy poses a significant challenge for traditional MOC calculation. The OpenMOC code [10] is employed to perform the transport calculation of this problem, and a fine quadrature set with 48 azimuthal angles and 6 Tabuchi-Yamamoto polar angles are utilized. However, as shown in Figure 2, noticeable ray effect is observed in the spatial flux distribution. Neutrons streaming through these gaps follow the specific, discrete directions of the MOC quadrature, which leads to artificially high flux values along these paths. This highlights the challenge of deterministic MOC for problems with strong transport effect.

Figure 1. Geometry of lattice problem

Table I. Cross-sections of lattice problem

Region	Total XS (cm^{-1})	Scattering XS (cm^{-1})	Source strength ($\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
Red	10	0	1
Black	10	0	0
Blue	1	1	0

Figure 2. Spatial flux of lattice problem calculated by OpenMOC

3.2. TRRM Results

Based on the content of Section 2, this study assumes that the TRRM can handle strongly anisotropic fluxes caused by transport effects without special treatments or excessive angular refinement, provided that the uncertainty of the final result converges. The uncertainty of TRRM is controlled by the total sampling amount, which is a production of both the number of characteristic rays per batch (N) and the tracking length of each ray (L). Therefore, the convergence behavior of TRRM is investigated by systematically varying N (while holding L constant) and L (while holding N constant) to verify the

assumption. For TRRM calculation, a uniform $1\text{ cm} \times 1\text{ cm}$ FSR meshes are adopted, and 200 batches of transport sweeps are performed with first 100 serve as inactive batches for source convergence. The neutron flux distribution along the red line ($y=0.5\text{ cm}$) in Figure 1 is selected for examination. This particular profile, located completely outside all absorbers, is strongly influenced by transport effects.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 illustrate the variations of the neutron flux distribution as a function of N (with L fixed at 100 cm) and L (with N fixed at 100), respectively. As either N or L increases, the total number of ray segments sampled increases, causing the statistical uncertainty (represented by error bars) to decrease. In all cases, the TRRM solution converges toward the reference solution, demonstrating that the accuracy is governed by statistical convergence rather than by a fixed angular discretization error. In TRRM, a larger N means more angles are sampled for the transport sweep. However, because a new, random set of angles is generated for every batch, the final converged solution (which averages many batches) is not sensitive to the N used in a single batch. To validate this, the specific calculation is performed using a sufficient total tracking length ($64,000\text{ cm}$) but with N set to only 10 . The flux distribution along with the $y=0.5\text{ cm}$ and the global flux distribution are presented in Figure 5, as shown, even a very small N can achieve an accurate result provided the total tracking length is sufficient.

Figure 3. Spatial flux of lattice problem versus number of characteristics rays ($L=100\text{ cm}$)

Nevertheless, a larger N and a smaller L is recommended since it yields a final result with lower statistical uncertainty. Figure 6 presents the comparison of the relative uncertainty for two cases with identical total tracking length but different N and L . The case with a larger N has noticeable smaller flux uncertainty than the case with a smaller N . This can be explained that a larger N reduces the batch-to-batch statistical fluctuations. Table II tabulates the average FSR segment in a single FSR and its

uncertainty with varying number of characteristic rays. The L for different N is adjusted to keep a constant total tracking length. It can be observed that although different values of N yield very similar numbers of average FSR segments, a larger N reduces its uncertainty. Since the final TRRM result is the statistical average of many transport sweeps, employing a larger N mitigates the statistical fluctuations between batches, thereby lowering the uncertainty of the final result.

To quantitatively evaluate the superiority of TRRM's stochastic quadrature, we performed a systematic convergence study comparing the average flux error of THETA and OpenMOC against the total number of MOC integrations. In traditional MOC, the accuracy is strictly limited by the fixed angular quadrature; when the number of integrations is insufficient, OpenMOC produces significant errors due to pronounced ray effects. However, TRRM explores a new set of angles in each iteration, allowing it to achieve a specified accuracy with significantly fewer total integrations than the deterministic MOC. As shown in *Figure 7*, the average error of TRRM remains consistently lower than that of MOC across the entire range of computational effort, confirming that TRRM is more efficient at resolving strongly anisotropic transport problems under constrained computational resources.

Figure 4. Spatial flux of lattice problem versus tracking length of characteristics rays ($N=100$)

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the capability of the Random Ray Method (TRRM) to resolve problems characterized by strong transport effect is investigated. A challenging lattice problem, featuring with strong absorbers arranged in a checkerboard pattern, is selected since strong transport effect exists at the gap between

absorbers and scatters. While the conventional Method of Characteristics (MOC) exhibits significant ray effects, the TRRM, which employs stochastic angular sampling, successfully captured the complex flux distribution without such artifacts. Numerical results confirm that TRRM's accuracy is governed by statistical uncertainty, not angular discretization error, and this uncertainty can be systematically reduced by increasing the total tracking length. Furthermore, for a fixed total tracking length, the optimal strategy is to use a larger number of rays per batch and a shorter tracking length. This approach minimizes batch-to-batch statistical fluctuations, thereby reducing the final uncertainty. In summary, the TRRM is validated as a robust and high-fidelity method for strongly anisotropic transport problems. Future work should focus on a rigorous comparison with MOC to further explain its advantage. Besides, the theory of TRRM's error estimation and the impact of inter-batch correlation on its variance estimation should also be investigated in future.

Figure 5. TRRM results for lattice problem with specified parameters

Figure 6. Relative uncertainty distribution of flux in lattice problem under different parameters

Table II. Average FSR tracking segment and its uncertainty versus number of characteristic rays

Number of characteristic rays	Average FSR tracking segment	Uncertainty
10	130.52	12.84
40	130.63	6.49
160	130.53	3.18
640	130.80	1.50

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Figure 7. Average flux error versus number of MOC integrations

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